

THE ROLE OF HIGHLY SELECTIVE NON-STEROIDAL ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS IN SURGICAL DENTISTRY

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ABSTRACT

NNT (number needed to treat), which is the average number of patients that need to be treated to achieve a 50% reduction in pain after 4 to 6 hours, is used as an indicator of the analgesic efficacy of a particular pharmacological drug.

In the practice of oral surgery surgical interventions on the organs and tissues of the mouth are often complicated by inflammatory process, which is accompanied in varying degrees of severity of the pain syndrome [2]. Timely reduction of pain syndrome intensity or its elimination significantly improves the well-being of patients in the departments of surgical dentistry of medical and preventive treatment facilities, improves their quality of life, and decreases the disability rate of the working population [3]. Wisdom teeth are known to be the cause of 7.3 % of adult patients' visits to dentists and surgeons [1]. Severe pain increases the stress on almost all vital body systems. The main cause is the autonomic response and the associated tachycardia, increased heart muscle activity and oxygen consumption by the heart. Inadequate anaesthesia in the post-operative period can lead to disruption of respiratory, endocrine and immune system

function, depletion of body and mental energy reserves, and significantly increases the risk of conditions such as respiratory distress syndrome, intestinal paresis and cardiovascular accidents. Lower wisdom teeth (69.05 %) are more often affected than upper wisdom teeth (30.95 %) [5]. At different ages, acute pericoronitis (29.25%), chronic periodontitis (19.61%), dystopia and/or retention (15.99%), superficial and moderate dental caries (11.68%), and acute and worsened chronic periodontitis (7.82%) occur among wisdom teeth pathology in both men and women [5, 7]. Less common reasons for referral to a dental surgeon are pulpitis (6.12%), deep caries (5.56%), periodontitis (3.74%), and mandibular radicular cysts (0.23%) [6, 9]. In the vast majority of cases, wisdom teeth are extracted for diseases of the pulp, periodontium, periodontium as well as for retention and/or dystopia, regardless of gender or age [10]. In more than half of all

cases, the post-operative period is complicated by purulent inflammatory processes in the extraction site (alveolitis), despite using modern instruments (12), and these are accompanied by severe pain that is difficult to treat (13). Therefore, the early management of pain syndrome in the practice of surgical dentistry is an urgent task of immediate application [4, 8]. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are widely used by dentists for this purpose [6, 10]. This is also evidenced by data from the TOPAR8 score, which indicates complete relief of pain after 8 hours [10]. For example, the analgesic effect of the highly selective NSAID etoricoxib has been shown to occur after 24 minutes of administration and lasts for 24 hours. Considering that highly selective NSAIDs, etoricoxib in particular, are currently available in 30 mg, 60 mg, 80 mg and 120 mg tablets, we found it useful for the clinical practice of dental surgery to assess the effectiveness of etoricoxib in different dosages in the occurrence of complications after extraction of the lower wisdom tooth, accompanied by pain syndrome of different severity. Odontogenic inflammatory diseases are characterised by a pronounced sense of pain due to the peculiarities of the tissues of the maxillofacial region, in particular the abundant innervation and vascularisation.

The intensity of the sense of pain requires adequate pain relief not only during surgical interventions required for the treatment of odontogenic inflammatory diseases, but also in the postoperative period of patient management.

Numerous scientific works have demonstrated good therapeutic efficacy of naproxen and aceclofenac used in medicine as monotherapy .

The vast majority of studies on the therapeutic potential and safety of aceclofenac have been performed in individuals suffering from rheumatic diseases. However, we have not found any scientific studies on this drug in dental practice in the scientific literature. In the available literature we could not find data about immunological activity of an oral liquid in application of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs for treatment of odontogenic inflammatory diseases.

Objective of the study: Improved efficacy of treatment of maxillary alveolitis using non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

Materials and methods of research: 27 people with maxillary alveolitis and 17 healthy volunteers without serious comorbid somatic pathology and with sanitized oral cavity were under observation and treatment.

Patients with odontogenic inflammatory diseases were divided into 3 groups randomized according to their age and sex; their examination was carried out by the same methods, but the complex of prescribed medicines. The criteria for selection of patients with odontogenic inflammatory diseases in one or another study group were: the intensity of pain in the first hours after surgical intervention, the nature of the accompanying somatic pathology. The criterion for selection of patients in group 1 was "low intensity" pain. The criterion for selection to group 2 was pain of "medium to high intensity": a score of 4 to 10. Group 3 consisted of patients with varying intensities of pain. The examination of patients included basic and additional methods of investigation. The basic examination methods were performed on the patients at the first and each follow-up

visit, and included a thorough history, external and intraoral examination.

The degree of inflammatory contracture of the masticatory muscles was determined according to the presence and character of mouth opening restriction. For subsequent analysis of the data obtained, each degree of inflammatory contracture was assigned a score equivalent to the degree value.

"1" - mouth opening up to 3 cm - minor degree of inflammatory contracture - 1 point

"2" - mouth opening up to 2 cm - moderate degree of inflammatory contracture - 2 points

"3" - mouth opening up to 0.5 cm - severe inflammatory contracture - 3 points.

During the intraoral examination, attention was paid to the condition of the mucous membrane: change of colour, humidity of the mucosa, presence of edema, ulcers or wound surfaces, infiltrates, exudate. The level of hygiene, the nature of the relationship of the dentition, the condition of the teeth, periodontal tissues were evaluated. Additional methods of examination included radiological (X-ray and ultrasound) and laboratory tests.

Radiological methods of investigation were carried out on the day of initial treatment of patients in order to specify the diagnosis and differential diagnosis, and included intraoral radiography or orthopantomography.

Laboratory tests of the mixed saliva, were used to assess the indicators of the local

immune protection factors of the oral cavity, both in the norm and as criteria for the effectiveness of the treatment carried out. Local immune protection factors were studied on the day of treatment and on the 7th day after the start of treatment.

Pain sense was carefully evaluated in patients with odontogenic inflammatory diseases both at the time of initial examination before treatment and during the phase of therapy. To assess the dynamics of pain, we used a scale developed by Professor S. T. T. Sokhov.

1 point - the postoperative course is completely painless: within 2 hours, 4 hours, 6 hours, 12 hours, the first day, the second day, the third day, the fourth day, the fifth day after the dental intervention;

2 points - the postoperative course is slightly painful for - 2 hours, 4 hours, 6 hours, 12 hours, the first day, second day, third day, fourth day, fifth day after the dental treatment, which does not require additional medication and pain relief

3 points - the postoperative course is accompanied by significant pain for - 2 hours, 4 hours, 6 hours, 12 hours, the first day, second day, third day, fourth day, fifth day after the dental intervention, which requires additional medication and pain relief. The results of the score allowed monitoring the intensity of pain during the course of the inflammatory process, which was recorded in the form of a table in the individual patient report.

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1. We have found that the severity of pain differs according to nosology and period of illness. At the time of presenting to the clinic the most severe pain is in patients diagnosed with alveolitis.
2. In an analysis of the sense of pain, we found that a reduction in pain intensity at the end of the treatment was registered in each group of patients examined. On the 5th day of follow-up the intensity of pain reached approximately the same values in all the groups studied,

as indicated by the absence of significant differences at this time ($P > 0.05$). However, the course and nature of pain manifestations in different pharmacological courses had significant differences, especially in the first postoperative hours, up to the first day of observation.

3. So, by the 4th observation hour in the group №1 the intensity of pain sense had not reliably decreased by 6,85 % ($P > 0,05$), in the group №2 reliably decreased by 27,4% ($P < 0,05$), in the comparison group reliable increase of pain sense intensity by 50% ($P < 0,001$) was determined. At the 6- and 12-hour follow-up periods, intensity of pain sensation was significantly lower in the mono- and consecutive courses of NSAIDs than in the comparison group ($P < 0.0001$; $P < 0.02$).
4. It should be noted that the decrease in pain intensity during naproxen use was statistically significant in all cases, in contrast to periods with aceclofenac, where the decrease in pain intensity was not statistically significant. The unreliable character of changes in pain intensity between periods of observation in patients while using acetylophenac, is associated with a less pronounced analgesic effect of the latter.
5. Conclusions: A mono-course of NSAIDs is thus effective in controlling "low intensity" pain. A sequential course has an effective analgesic effect in cases of "moderate to severe" pain while using naproxen. With a switch to acetylophenac for high intensity pain, the analgesic effect weakens. This may warrant an extension of the use of naproxen in terms of 'moderate to severe' pain.
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